

Effects of temperature on host feeding in *Cardiochiles philippinensis* (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), a larval parasitoid of rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*

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Many climatologists agree that ecologically significant warming will occur during the next century. Recent estimates suggested that warming as high as 3 ± 1.5 °C could be possible. This will affect not only the distribution and survival of species but also the interspecific interaction, such as competition and predation.

The parasitoid, *C. philippinensis*, is a solitary endoparasitoid of the larvae of the rice leaffolder (RLF) *C. medinalis*. It is commonly found in ricefields of the Philippines, with field parasitism as high as 60%.

We evaluated the effects of temperature on *C. philippinensis* larvae. The laboratory experiments were conducted at six temperatures with six host density levels of 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 32 third-instar larvae. Each density was replicated 5 times. Forty-day-old IR36 potted plants were used to support the RLF larvae. These were enclosed in cylindrical mylar cages (23 cm diam and 60 cm high). One pair of 2-d-old mated parasitoids were introduced into each arena and placed in the designated chambers maintained at 25, 28, 30, 33, 35, and 40 ± 0.5 °C, 70 ± 4% relative humidity, and 12:12 illumination conditions. The larvae were collected after 24 h and dissected using a binocular microscope to determine parasitism.

The data were fitted to the random parasitoid equation,

$$N_a = N_t \{1 - \exp[-aTP_t / (1 + aT_h N_t)]\}$$

where N_a is the number of hosts attacked, N_t is the number of hosts available, a is the instantaneous search rate, T is the total time of the experiment, P_t is the number of parasitoids, and T_h is the parasitoid handling time.

Parameters of functional response of *C. philippinensis* feeding on RLF larvae.

Temperature (°C)	Searching rate/h	Handling time (h)	R ²	F value
25	1.77 ± 1.30	0.29 ± 0.04	0.85	81.14
28	1.51 ± 0.66	0.25 ± 0.03	0.93	183.06
30	0.92 ± 0.46	0.31 ± 0.05	0.86	85.04
33	0.88 ± 0.63	0.45 ± 0.09	0.76	44.67
35	0.53 ± 0.33	0.56 ± 0.12	0.74	40.70
40	Parasitoid unable to survive			

A nonlinear least squares technique using the PROCNLIN procedure available in SAS was applied to fit the data to the equation and to estimate the parameters a and T_h (see table). The functional responses are presented in the figure. At 40 °C, the parasitoids were unable to survive.

Searching efficiencies decreased gradually with increasing temperatures.

Functional response curves of *C. philippinensis*.

This relationship was best described by a linear model: $a = 4.80 - 0.12t$ where t is temperature in °C. The handling time declined slightly at 20 °C, but increased subsequently with increase in temperature. A quadratic relationship described this response well: $T_h = 3.88 - 0.27t + 0.005t^2$.

Elevated temperature regimes tend to reduce parasitism of *C. philippinensis* on RLF larvae. This implies that global warming may decrease mortality of RLF larvae caused by this parasitoid. This

study, however, is restricted to the Philippine population of *C. philippinensis*. These more tolerant populations may exist in other areas, particularly in environments frequently

subjected to higher temperature stresses. More tolerant strains may be introduced to augment biological control of RLF in the Philippines. ■

Research methodology

Detection of rice tungro bacilliform virus in nonvector insect species following genomic amplification

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Rice tungro disease (RTD) caused by rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) has a semipersistent relationship with its principal vector *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant). This implies there is no replication of virus particles in the vector, and the active site for association of the virus is in the anterior part of the gut, namely the pharynx, cibarium, or possibly the stylets. The very low quantities of virus(es) acquired during feeding are only retained for a relatively short period, up to 3-5 d. To detect RTBV in single viruliferous insects, we used Ampliwax polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification procedure in which a small fragment (569 bp) of RTBV DNA was amplified from the total nucleic acid extract of a single viruliferous insect and detected on agarose gel.

Total nucleic acid extract of insect tissue was prepared by grinding the individual insect in a microcentrifuge tube containing the extraction buffer, (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.3, 10 mM EDTA, 10 mM NaCl, 0.5% SDS, and 1 mg proteinase K/ml). The contents were transferred to eppendorf tubes and incubated at 65 °C for 2 h. The samples were extracted with TE phenol/chloroform (1:1 v/v) and then with chloroform and isoamyl alcohol (24:1 v/v). Total genomic DNA was precipitated by adding 3 M ammonium acetate (1/10V), glycogen (1 µl), and 2/3 volume of cold absolute alcohol to the aqueous phase and incubated at -20 °C overnight. Pellets formed by the centrifugation at 13,000

rpm for 20 min were washed carefully with 70% alcohol. Excess alcohol was removed by vacuum drying. The pellets were suspended in 30 µl of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8). The nucleic acid concentration was estimated by gel electrophoresis of samples on 1% agarose gel. Twenty-mer primers were designed according to the published sequence of RTBV. The plus strand primer (5'-CCTGTGAAACCCAATACTGC-3') and minus strand primer (5'-GCTGAGGTGCTACATAGGTT-3')

1. PCR products resolved in 2% agarose gel, stained with ethidium bromide and visualized by UV illumination. The DNA template used was M = size marker (100-1000 bp); lanes 1 and 2 = total genomic DNA from RTBV-infected plant (positive control); lanes 3-12 = total genomic DNA of *N. virescens* (top) and 10 *N. nigropictus* (bottom); lanes 13 and 14 = total genomic DNA from non-viruliferous insects (negative control).

2. PCR products resolved in 2% agarose gel, stained with ethidium bromide and visualized by UV illumination. The DNA template used was M = size marker (300-1000 bp); top lane 1 = total genomic DNA from RTBV-infected plant (positive control); lane 2 = total genomic DNA from nonviruliferous insect (negative control); lanes 3-14 = total genomic DNA of 12 *Nilaparvata lugens*. Bottom: lanes 1-2 = total genomic DNA from RTBV-infected plant (positive control); lanes 3-12 = total genomic DNA of 10 *Recilia dorsalis*; lanes 13 and 14 = total genomic DNA from nonviruliferous insect (negative control).